

STRESS ANALYSIS AROUND AN OPEN HOLE OF CFRP MODIFIED WITH GNPs

Stella Peloni^{1,2}, Nikolaos Koutroumanis¹, Panagiotis Nektarios Pappas¹, Nikolaos Kontis¹, Costas Galiotis^{1,2,*}

¹Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences, Foundation of Research and Technology, Hellas, Platani St., Patras, Greece

²Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, Patras, Greece

Outline

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs)

Carbon nanofillers (CN)

Stress concentration properties of CN enhanced FRPs

Novelty – Scope

Techniques

Results

Conclusions

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs)

PROS

- ✓ High strength-to-weight ratio
- ✓ Excellent fatigue properties
- ✓ Corrosion resistance
- ✓ Design flexibility

CONS

- Sensitive in adverse environmental conditions
- Low resistance to impact
- Delamination
- Susceptible to discontinuities/defects

Delamination: The layers of a composite material start to separate or peel apart.

Fiber-matrix debonding: Debonding between the fiber and matrix is weakened or lost.

Cracks: Small or large fractures in the composite material.

Notches/Holes: Occur due to manufacturing errors, voids in the material, or damage caused during handling or use.

Need for quantifying and reducing those regions

Ref. Fabrizio Sarasini et al. "Quasi-Static and Low-Velocity Impact Behavior of Intraply Hybrid Flax/Basalt Composites"

Ref. Chan-Joo Lee et al. "Design of Hole-Clinching Process for Joining CFRP and Aluminum Alloy Sheet"

Ref. Christopher Baker et al. "Transverse cracking in carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites: Modal acoustic emission and peak frequency analysis"

Minimizing their effect on the performance of the CFRPs

Carbon nanofillers (CN)

Reinforcement type

Configuration

Classification

Particle

Additive

DISCONTINUOUS

Layer

Nanolaminate

CONTINUOUS

Fibre

CN-enhanced FRPs

HYBRID

Stress concentration properties of CN enhanced FRPs

<i>Type of Composite</i>	<i>Nanofiller</i>	<i>Weight fraction %</i>	<i>Investigated properties</i>	<i>Improvement %</i>	<i>References</i>
CFRP	GNP	0.5	G_{Ic}	61	Kostagiannopoulou et al. (2021), Engineering Fracture Mechanics
CFRP	GNP	0.5	G_{IIc}	25	Kostagiannopoulou et al. (2021), Engineering Fracture Mechanics
CFRP	GNP	3	G_{Ic}	60.4	Vijay K. Srivastava et al. (2017), Engineering Fracture Mechanics
CFRP	GO	0.5	G_{Ic}	49	Kostagiannopoulou et al. (2015), Composites Science and Technology
GFRP	CNT	0.1	Strength of an open hole composite	27	Pothenis J et al. (2021), Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing

- Investigation of the damage evolution of open hole GFRP utilizing **DIC** method
- In-situ direct non-contact measurement of displacements/strains-Non destructive technique

Addition of GNPs in notched CFRPs → Investigation of stress concentration around the circular notch via Remote Raman technique.

Remote Raman

- ✓ Non-destructive analysis
- ✓ Real-time analysis
- ✓ Large area coverage
- ✓ Flexibility
- ✓ Reduced safety risks

Validation of
results

- Numerically, Finite Element Analysis

- Analytically, Tan's FWC factor

$$\frac{K_T}{K_T^\infty} = \left\{ \frac{3 \left(1 - \frac{2R}{w}\right)}{2 + \left(1 - \frac{2R}{w}\right)^3} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2R}{w}\right)^6 (K_T^\infty - 3) \left[1 - \left(\frac{2R}{w}\right)^2\right]^{-1} \right\}$$

A diagram of a rectangular plate with a circular notch of radius R. The plate is subjected to a tensile load P. The notch is centered on the horizontal axis. The diagram shows the stress distribution around the notch, with the maximum stress σ_{max} occurring at the top and bottom edges of the notch. The diagram also shows the geometry of the notch, with points A, B, and O labeled.

➤ Fibres' calibration curves

Micro tensile testing machine-Deben

Different Strain Levels

Remote Raman Spectroscopy

➤ Measurements for different applied strains

Fibre Calibration
curves

Stress/strain
in fibres

Basic model
creation-Neat CFRP

Boundary conditions:

$$U_1=U_2=U_3=0$$
$$U_{R1}=U_{R2}=U_{R3}=0$$

Boundary conditions:

$$U_1= \text{Applied displacement}$$
$$U_2=U_3=0$$
$$U_{R1}=U_{R2}=U_{R3}=0$$

Plies orientation: $[0]_s$

Python
scripting

Models' generation-
Modified CFRPs

Python
scripting

Stress/strain
extraction

Axial stress for infinite plate

$$\sigma_{xx}(x=0, y) = P + \frac{P}{\beta_1 - \beta_2} * \left\{ \frac{\beta_1^2}{1 - \beta_1} \left[1 - \frac{\beta_1 y}{\sqrt{R^2 + \beta_1^2(y^2 - R^2)}} \right] - \frac{\beta_2^2}{1 - \beta_2} \left[1 - \frac{\beta_2 y}{\sqrt{R^2 + \beta_2^2(y^2 - R^2)}} \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

β_1, β_2 are related to elastic properties of the composite.

Tan's finite width correction factor (FWC)

$$\frac{K_T}{K_T^\infty} = \left\{ \frac{3 \left(1 - \frac{2R}{w}\right)}{2 + \left(1 - \frac{2R}{w}\right)^3} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2R}{w} M\right)^6 (K_T^\infty - 3) \left[1 - \left(\frac{2R}{w}\right)^2 \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Axial stress for finite plate

$$\sigma_{xx,finite}(x=0, y) = \text{FWC} * \sigma_{xx}(x=0, y) \quad (3)$$

Neat Samples-Different Strain Levels

- Maximum stress is observed at the hole tip
- Max stress decays as the distance from the hole increases
- Stress reaches a plateau at distances greater than 1000 μm

Stress concentration factor K :

- Fibre fracture is assumed to occur between 0.15 and 0.2% of the external applied strain, where K decays dramatically
- Maximum K at the notch tip is observed in **0.05%** applied strain

Selected strain step for all the following cases (Neat and GNPs enhanced CFRPs)

➤ 0.05% External applied strain

$$K = \frac{\sigma \text{ at any point}}{\sigma_{\infty}}$$

- Analytical —
- Numerical —
- Experimental ■

Remarks

- The experimental value of K at the notch tip, in neat CFRPs, equals to 4.5
- The analytical and numerical methods overestimate the K value up to 19% and 25%
- The experimentally defined stress concentration profile agrees with the analytical and numerical ones
- Similar behaviour of the K profile is presented for the modified CFRPs
- The analytical and numerical methods overestimate the K value up to 30% in case of 2wt% GNPs enhanced CFRP

	<i>Numerical & Analytical Models</i>	<i>Experiments</i>
Voids/ Inclusions/ Fibre breakages	X	✓
GNPs Geometry	X	✓
GNPs Orientation	X	✓
GNPs Properties	✓	✓

Determination of K reduction➤ 0.05% External applied strain

- No significant difference of K values in the far field
- Apparent difference at the notch edge
- K decrease up to 2% for 0.5wt% GNP enhanced CFRP
- K decrease up to 8.8% for 1wt% GNP enhanced CFRP
- K decrease up to 12% for 2wt% GNP enhanced CFRP

GNPs act as a good reinforcement \rightarrow Part of the stress is distributed to the GNPs \rightarrow The fibres bare less stresses \rightarrow K reduction
 GNPs have been deformed with a sensitivity of $-4 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ far from the hole

GNPs have been deformed with a sensitivity of $-10 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ around the hole

Conclusions

- Stress reaches a plateau at distances greater than 1000 μm
- The experimental value of K at the notch tip equals to 4.5 for the neat composite
- Maximum K decrease up to 12% for 2wt% enhanced CFRP as observed from experimental data
- Discrepancy between experimental and analytical/numerical K value at hole edge
- The experimentally defined K profile agrees with the analytical and numerical ones
- GNPs act as a good reinforcement since part of the stress is distributed to the GNPs K reduction
- Remote Raman is a high-sensitivity method to in-situ measure the deformation via a non-destructive manner and provide the data in real time

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*For your
attention!!!*